

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

APPLIED CONSERVATION PRACTICES AND DEVELOPMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE PROTECTION OF *PANCRATIUM MARITIMUM* L. IN THE COASTAL ZONE OF LARA, ANTALYA

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Abstract

Pancratium maritimum L. (sea daffodil) is a characteristic psammophytic geophyte of coastal dune ecosystems in the Mediterranean and Black Sea basins, whose populations are highly vulnerable to anthropogenic pressure associated with tourism, urbanization, and dune degradation. The present study aims to analyze the applied conservation practices for the protection of the species in the coastal dune zone of Lara Beach (Antalya, Turkey) and to assess their effectiveness under conditions of intensive recreational pressure. The study was conducted during the period December 2025 – January 2026 on a representative dune area of about 12 ha and includes field observations and direct counting of individuals in unprotected natural sites, fenced natural sites, and areas of targeted cultivation. The results show clear differences in population density, with the lowest values recorded in unprotected sites and the highest in cultivated zones. The obtained data confirm the positive effect of physical protection and active management on the condition of the populations. The presence of invasive ornamental species, especially *Carpobrotus edulis*, was identified as a significant long-term risk to dune ecosystems. The study highlights the need for an integrated approach to the conservation of *P. maritimum*, combining territorial protection, control of invasive alien species, and sustainable management of coastal tourist areas.

Keywords: *Pancratium maritimum*; coastal dunes; conservation measures; tourist pressure; invasive species; Turkey

Introduction

Pancratium maritimum L. (sea daffodil) is a coastal psammophytic geophyte characteristic of sandy beaches and dune systems in the Mediterranean and Black Sea basins, where it forms scattered populations in mobile and fixed dunes. The biology and reproductive strategy of the species are closely adapted to dynamic sandy habitats, which makes the condition of its populations directly dependent on the conservation status and functioning of dune ecosystems (Medrano et al., 1999; Medrano et al., 2000; Apostolova, 2015).

Despite its relatively wide geographical distribution, numerous studies indicate that local populations of *P. maritimum* are highly vulnerable to anthropogenic pressure, including coastal urbanization, development of tourist infrastructure, recreational trampling, and mechanical destruction of dunes. These factors lead to a reduction in population size, reproductive success, and spatial integrity, with negative effects being particularly pronounced in intensively used beach areas (Demir et al., 2010; Pouris & Rhizopoulou, 2018).

Therefore, the scientific literature increasingly supports the understanding that effective conservation of *Pancratium maritimum* in practice represents conservation of coastal dune habitats through the combination of measures aimed at limiting direct damage to plants and spatial management of human activities on dunes.

Bulgaria: legal framework and field-based measures

Pancratium maritimum L. is included both in the Red List of Bulgarian vascular plants with the category

Endangered (EN) (Petrova, Vladimirov, 2009) and in the Red Data Book of Bulgaria (Apostolova, 2015), reflecting its high vulnerability and the need for targeted measures for the conservation of its coastal habitats. At the national level, the species is protected under the Biological Diversity Act, which establishes a regime including prohibition of destruction and damage to individuals and obligations for habitat protection (Biological Diversity Act, 2002). The Act emphasizes the implementation of plans and measures for threatened species, including monitoring, population support, and control of alien and invasive species. Part of the species' localities fall within protected areas and sites of the Natura 2000 ecological network, which links its conservation to territorial management and restrictions on permissible activities. One of the clearest examples of targeted territorial protection is the maintained reserve “Pyasachnata liliya” near Sozopol, designated with the main objective of conserving the largest locality of the species in Bulgaria. The practical implementation of measures in Bulgaria focuses on limiting trampling, prohibiting the passage of motor vehicles, physical fencing and directing visitor flow, as well as banning the collection of plants (Apostolova et al., 2015).

Europe: a habitat-oriented conservation model

Pancratium maritimum L. is assessed as Least Concern (LC) within the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Vicedo, 2018), with the assessment reflecting the wide distribution of the species in the Mediterranean Basin. Nevertheless, the document emphasizes that conservation of the species is closely linked to the

preservation and sustainable management of coastal sandy dune habitats, recommending the application of local measures to limit anthropogenic pressure and to monitor populations, especially in tourist-intensive coastal areas.

The main instrument for the conservation of these ecosystems in the EU is the Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, which requires the introduction of necessary conservation measures in protected sites (European Commission, 1992). According to Article 6 of the Directive, Member States are obliged to prevent the deterioration of natural habitats and the habitats of species within Natura 2000 sites. Typical dune habitats in which *Pancratium maritimum* occurs are included in Annex I of the Directive as priority or significant habitats. In the EUNIS database, the species is indicated as not being directly included in EU legal texts, confirming the indirect nature of its protection through habitats (EEA, 2026). In addition, Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 on invasive alien species establishes a framework for limiting pressure on dune ecosystems, although *Pancratium maritimum* is not directly subject to this regulation (European Parliament & Council, 2014).

Turkey: a species-oriented and restrictive approach

In Turkey, the scientific basis for the conservation of *Pancratium maritimum* L. is laid down in the Red Data Book of Turkish Plants, where the species is classified as endangered (EN) at the national level (Ekim et al., 2000). This conservation status underpins the application of strict regulatory measures primarily aimed at preventing removal from the wild and trade in bulbs. A key regulatory instrument is the Regulation on the Collection from Nature, Production and Export of Natural Flower Bulbs, published in the Resmî Gazete (Republic of Türkiye, 2017), which introduces permit regimes, quotas, and complete bans for a number of bulbous plants. In a managerial and policy context, this restrictive approach is clearly formulated in the review report by Kızmaz (2000), where *Pancratium maritimum* is listed among natural bulbous species for which collection and export from the wild are explicitly prohibited

in order to prevent overexploitation and the risk of local extinction. Scientific publications on *Pancratium maritimum* in Turkey consider the species an indicator of the condition of coastal dune habitats, emphasizing that its effective conservation depends on control of tourism activities, recreational pressure, and secondary development, which justifies the introduction of a complete ban on collection and trade of the species from the wild (Demir et al., 2010). At the same time, Turkish institutions apply significant administrative sanctions for damaging or picking plants, which has a clearly deterrent effect (Anadolu Ajansı, 2023). In parallel, studies are conducted and methods related to the restoration of sea daffodil populations are applied. The study by Tatlı and Çalıskan (2005), carried out on Mediterranean ecotypes of *Pancratium maritimum* from the Adana and Hatay regions, experimentally demonstrates that the application of controlled nitrogen doses (0–9 kg/da N) allows successful ex situ cultivation as an effective strategy for conserving natural populations along the Mediterranean coast of Turkey, without additional pressure on dune ecosystems.

The aim of the present study is to examine the applied conservation practices for the protection of *Panocratium maritimum* in the coastal dune zone of Lara Beach (Antalya, Turkey) and, on this basis, to outline opportunities for complementing measures for the conservation of coastal dune habitats.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted in the coastal dune zone of Lara Beach (Antalya, Turkey), located along the eastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea. The study area is defined as a coastal dune section of Lara Beach (Antalya, Turkey), centered around a geographical reference point with coordinates 36°51'12.5" N, 30°53'04.8" E, with the investigation covering a linear segment approximately 2 km in length, symmetrically distributed in both directions (1 km east and 1 km west) from the central point (Fig. 1). With an average width of the dune belt of about 60 m, the total area of the representative study site amounts to approximately 12 ha.

Fig.1. Study area

The area falls within a Mediterranean climate zone, characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. The mean annual temperature in the Antalya region is about 18–19°C. During the winter period (December–January), average temperatures typically range between 8 and 15°C, with negative values being rare and short-lived. The mean annual precipitation ranges between 900 and 1100 mm, with the majority of rainfall concentrated in late autumn and winter. The summer period is distinctly dry. These climatic conditions favor the development of xerophytic and psammophytic vegetation characteristic of Mediterranean coastal dune ecosystems. Positive winter temperatures allow prolonged or continuous vegetation activity in a number of Mediterranean geophytes, including *Pancratium maritimum*. The habitats of *P. maritimum* are restricted to sandy dunes and transitional zones between the beach and the back-dune vegetation. The soil substrate consists of well-drained, nutrient-poor sands subject to salinization, wind erosion, and mechanical disturbance (trampling, beach cleaning).

The coastal zone of Lara Beach represents a representative example of a heavily tourist-loaded Mediterranean beach, where intensive recreational use, construction, and decorative landscaping exert prolonged and combined pressure on dune ecosystems and populations of *Panocratium maritimum*.

Methods

Field observations were carried out during the period December 2025 – January 2026. The study has an

observational and descriptive character, without experimental interventions and without damage to plants or habitats.

Depending on the applied conservation measures and management regime, three types of sites were distinguished:

1. Natural sites without fencing – dune areas with free access and no physical protection;
2. Natural sites with fencing – dune areas with restricted access through fences and information boards;
3. Cultivation zones – areas within the tourist infrastructure where *P. maritimum* is deliberately planted and maintained.

The main quantitative indicator was population density, determined by direct counting of individuals and expressed as number of individuals per square meter (ind./m²). In addition, phenological status, spatial distribution, the presence of conservation measures, and the presence of introduced ornamental plant species were recorded.

Results

Within the studied dune area, three main types of applied conservation measures were identified: (1) targeted cultivation of *Panocratium maritimum* within the tourist infrastructure; (2) physical protection of natural sites through fencing; and (3) installation of information boards aimed at restricting unauthorized access and increasing public awareness (Fig. 2). These measures create different management regimes that directly affect the spatial distribution and population density of the species.

Fig. 2. Examples of applied conservation measures for the protection of the population of *Pancratium maritimum* (photo P. Glogov)

Within the study area, populations of *Pancratium maritimum* are confined to small, fragmented dune patches occupying less than 1% of the total investigated area (12 ha). Clear differences in population density were recorded among the different types of sites (Fig. 3):

- Natural sites without fencing – on average about 1 individual/m²;
- Natural sites with fencing – on average about 2–3 individuals/m²;
- Cultivation zones – the highest values, ranging between 4–6 individuals/m².

Fig. 3. A – Cultivation zones of *Pancratium maritimum*; B – Natural sites with fencing; (photo P. Glogov)

Positive winter temperatures allow prolonged or continuous vegetation in a number of Mediterranean geophytes, including *Pancratium maritimum*. During the study period, a seed dispersal phase was recorded, combined with the presence of green vegetative leaves, indicating active winter vegetation of the species.

The most significant potential threat to *P. maritimum* is *Carpobrotus edulis* (Fig. 4), which forms

monodominant communities in places with dense projective cover (100%) and is cultivated for ornamental purposes in close proximity to dune habitats. To a lesser extent, the presence of *Ruellia simplex* (Acanthaceae) was recorded (in cultivated zones and at the periphery of natural sites).

Fig. 4. Population of *Carpobrotus edulis* in close proximity to *Pancreatium maritimum* (photo P. Glogov)

Discussion

The results clearly show that the applied conservation measures—fencing, installation of information boards, and cultivation of *Pancreatium maritimum*—have a positive effect on population density. The gradual increase in density from unprotected to protected and cultivated sites highlights the importance of active management under conditions of strong tourist pressure.

The observations of the present study are consistent with the results of an empirical study conducted along the western Black Sea coast of Turkey (Demir et al., 2010), which demonstrated that spatial protection of dune areas through fencing has a clearly positive effect on the condition of *Pancreatium maritimum* populations. In that study, protected sites were characterized by better population and reproductive indicators compared to freely accessible areas, with the role of anthropogenic disturbance clearly emphasized as a major limiting factor. A similar trend is observed in the Lara Beach area, where higher population density and more stable spatial distribution of the species are found in fenced and managed dune sites compared to unprotected zones. This similarity in results, regardless of differences in geographical location and degree of tourist pressure, confirms the importance of physical protection and spatial management as universal elements in the conservation of coastal dune habitats.

At the same time, invasive alien species, especially *Carpobrotus edulis*, represent a serious long-term risk to dune ecosystems, as they suppress native vegetation and alter habitat structure. Although *Ruellia simplex* is less widespread, its proven invasive potential

in other regions necessitates increased attention. In the context of coastal dune ecosystems, the results of the present study should be interpreted against the background of increasing pressure from invasive alien plant species, whose spread is closely linked to ornamental landscaping, infrastructure development, and tourist urbanization. A typical example is *Carpobrotus edulis*—a South African succulent with nearly global distribution, including the Mediterranean region and Turkey—which forms dense, long-lasting mats, suppresses native psammophytic vegetation, alters soil properties, and leads to a significant reduction in biodiversity in coastal habitats (O'Rourke & Lysaght, 2014).

Data for Turkey indicate that the country is particularly vulnerable to biological invasions due to its geographical position, intensive maritime traffic, and high diversity of climatic and floristic regions. To date, between several dozen and more than 80 invasive alien plant species have been documented in individual areas, including *Carpobrotus edulis* (Atasoy & Çorbacı, 2018).

The absence of an obligation to apply Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 in Turkey creates preconditions for uncontrolled use of ornamental introduced species, which may compromise the effectiveness of local conservation measures. The country lacks a comprehensive national regulatory framework, a specialized database, and mandatory monitoring of invasive alien species, making their control fragmented and largely reactive. In this context, experience from other regions shows that effective management of invasive ornamental spe-

cies cannot rely solely on mechanical or chemical removal but requires integrated, ecosystem-oriented approaches.

A representative example is *Ruellia simplex*—a widely used ornamental species that forms dense invasions in floodplain forests in the southeastern United States—where experimental studies demonstrate that targeted reintroduction of fast-establishing native species can significantly reduce the abundance and biomass of the invasive taxon through early competitive suppression (Smith et al., 2015). A similar approach, based on replacing invasive ornamental plants with suitable native psammophytic and dune species, could be of key importance for Turkish coastal zones as well, where the lack of regulatory restrictions on the introduction of ornamental species increases the risk of long-term degradation of *Pancreatium maritimum* habitats. Therefore, in the absence of regulatory control over invasive alien species in Turkey, successful conservation of the species requires not only physical protection of dune areas but also active management measures aimed at prevention, early containment, and ecological restoration of affected habitats.

Conclusion

The study shows that local conservation measures for the protection of *Pancreatium maritimum* in the coastal dune zone of Lara Beach are effective and lead to higher population densities in protected and cultivated sites. Nevertheless, the cultivation of invasive alien species, particularly *Carpobrotus edulis*, represents a significant risk to the long-term conservation of the species.

Effective conservation of the sea daffodil under conditions of intensive tourism requires an integrated approach combining physical protection of sites, public awareness, and restriction of the use of potentially invasive ornamental plants in coastal landscaping.

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